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The Elements of life

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Abstract

Article "Elements of Life" offers a hypothesis about the relationship of the phenomenon of traditional Chinese medicine with the physical laws. It shows the principle of forming a sequence of daily activity of the acupuncture meridians as a consequence of the Doppler effect in the process of flowing around the planet Earth by cosmic wind (by Ether). In accordance with this specification the daily structure of meridians had been built. It is suggested that the essence of the Chinese Qi (Chi) are vibrations of a certain range in the medium. Consequently, it became possible to set the interrelation of frequencies of the visible spectrum with certain meridians. It is shown that the topological relationship of ancient (barrier) points of the Five Elements (Wu-Shu points) are associated with the wave lengths of the so-called Qi. It is shown also that the essence of the Wu-Xing law is based on daily circulation patterns of meridians. The examples of the surrounding world, including pulses processes in the human body, are confirming the above mentioned theses. A correlation diagram between the main elements by Dr. Samohotsky A.S. (dissertation "The experience of the definition of medical laws", 1946) and the Five Elements of traditional Chinese philosophy is established. The above represented hypotheses are yet introduced in practice in form of pulse spectral analysis system.

Keywords

Chinese medicine, Physics, Daily cycle of acupuncture meridians, Ether, Spectrum

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Foreword

Modern official medicine is in crisis: this fact is known for a long time to many professionals. A huge amount of knowledge about the processes in the living body is accumulated, but our centenarians live for as long as

thousands of years ago. There are still incurable diseases that kill even representatives of medicine at the same way just like the ordinary folk.

Researchers in medical science look like a flea on an elephant's body. Each flea examines some minor detail and

pays almost no attention to what the others are doing around. It is doubtful that such quantitative approaches can be transformed into quality. Even trillions of fleas on the elephant will not be able to understand what they are dealing as a whole with.

Required is a different approach, allowing to change the perspective of the study review arbitrarily, in accordance with the current needs either to observe the elephant as a whole system, or as a part, or microscopically in a local order, as it is occurring nowadays.

This article is the result of rather long-term considerations and research in the area of pulse spectral analysis, searching for the supporting evidence of fresh models and ideas. Briefly, now facts clearly indicate the absolute dependence of life processes on the Earth on cosmic events, and it can be explained by the theories of old Physics of 19th century.

Primary Elements of physics: Space and its contents

Catching up solving a mystery of the life it is impossible to ignore such science as physics (from the ancient Greek φύσις – nature). In fact, we have to study the properties of the Universe (Cosmos): it's the largest (unlimited size) object we can image, which itself includes everything that exists. The recognition of the existence of such object, which includes most everything that can exist, is a contradictory statement. Indeed where is the Cosmos itself is located?

In addition, the vastness of Cosmos is difficult to grasp. The whole experience of life suggests that everything has its limits, that any event here has always a beginning and an end. However, to achieve practical results that will help us to improve the life, we can

accept the postulate of the infinitude of Cosmos, and put this principle to the base of our theory. After all, if we compare the size of our earthly world with the scale of the cosmos, from a practical point of view, the immensity of space should be allowed.

And, certainly, our theories we have to check by practice.

Further, in terms of research methodology, we rely on the principle of "Occam's Razor": to explain the phenomena and events of Nature used must be a minimum of objects and rules. This methodological approach is fully in line with the natural principle of the least action. In nature always the process wins which in order to achieve the maximum results will consume the minimum of energy. In other words, it's principle of optimum – the principle of the necessity and sufficiency – water always flows to the direction where it is easier to flow; nobody will scratch his (her) right ear with the left hand with no reason, and so on.

Any study and any science are based on a certain number of axioms and postulates, i.e. statements that do not require any proof. In our study, we use the postulate of genius Rene Descartes "In the Universe there is nothing but Ether and its vortexes."

Descartes postulate fully complies with the principle of "Occam's Razor", because it contains only two components which are composition of all things.

These two components are the scene – Cosmos, and the actor – Ether on the stage. With the help of this scene and actor Nature is playing the whole Cosmic grand show which is represented in the smallest details of vast multiplicity of processes and phenomena. The presence of only two above mentioned components of all

things is completely analogous to the semantic concepts of Yin and Yang in the Oriental philosophy. In our case we can name Cosmos (Space) as Yang (the Form) which is filled with Yin – Ether (the Content).

A blink of the cosmic eye
And what does it see?
I'll promise neither you or me.

With gravity at our feet its destiny
we meet
Grounded to the Earth like we're
blind from birth
We were never meant to really see
The full beauty of the Galaxies

A spectrum of colors
Rain a bow of feelings
Black holes swallowing
Dark twisted healings
Sun's shining moon
Guide our night to light

Reminding us to fight each fight.

Stephanie Nicole

Properties of Space

Space as a measure of length has two fundamental properties:

The first property of Space: it has three-dimensional measurements - via the intersection of two mutually perpendicular lines, you can draw only one single line that is perpendicular to the both intersecting lines. It means that at any number of operating forces near the given point of the intersection of 3 lines can be reduced just to three mutually perpendicular INDEPENDENT forces.

The three-dimensional measurement of Space is reflected in the physical phenomena, such as follows:

– The ancient Indian philosophy of the theory of the three doshas (Pita, Kapha, Vata) postulates the necessity and sufficiency of only three active principles in the human body;

– The result of the reaction of two chemicals will be different depending on the acidity status of the medium;

– The electromagnetic energy vector of Umov-Poynting is orthogonal both to the electric potential and the magnetic vector and so on.

With the help of three perpendicular lines intersecting at one point of Space it is possible to specify uniquely the coordinates of any point by values of the three distances from the point of the intersection of three lines (the center of the coordinates system) as orthogonal projections on the lines of the system of coordinates (Figures 1 & 2).

The description of physical processes through Space of the other dimension has a specific character (zero, one and two-dimensional space). In case with more than three dimensions, the description serves for calculation of some artificial mathematical models (four, five or more spaces) and in our opinion it has no relations to real physical processes (in fact it is violation of the "Occam's Razor" principles).

The second property of Space is isotropy when the conditions for movement in any direction of Space are not dependent on Space itself.

Properties of the Ether

The Ether as a material substance consists of superfine homogeneous particles, which have an absolute elasticity in collisions with each other and move at the same constant speed.

The Ether, as well as Space, has two main characteristics:

The first peculiarity is that due to the properties of the Ether's particles to interact elastically. It provides the endless moving and everlasting changes in the Universe, which was fixed in the great book of Chinese philosophy – the Book of Changes

Figure 1. Coordinate System of the Space. The center of the System may be any point of the Space, but if the point is selected it should be taken for all further calculation to save the continuity of the data

Figure 2. The set of points on the trajectory is the Minkowski's Space. Possibly the Minkowski's Space was introduced to hide the common sense

(I Ching). That infinitude movement represents the Energy itself: the force of countless particles of the Ether has no restrictions in the Universe (against any force there is always a more powerful force available). However, each particle of the Ether has equal and permanent speed in comparing with other particles. The speed of the sole particle of the Ether is a single quant of Energy in our Universe. Exactly this peculiarity of the Ether gives the opportunity to physicists to create their quantum theories.

During an equal period of time, all particles in the Ether complete the same path. It means that the time has similarity to Space: on the one hand time can be estimated by measuring the traveled distance, and on the oth-

er hand the distance may be predicted by measuring the time. It is obvious that this property of Ether in Space was used by famous mathematician Hermann Minkowski to create his theory of a pseudo-Euclidean space, where the time is the fourth dimension (The Minkowski space is the base of Einstein's relativity theory). However, in the opinion of the Author of this study, no real physical processes have relations to the Minkowski's space, and it is only a tool to record a trajectory of objects in three-dimensional space with time.

The Time phenomenon is a consequence of properties of the uniform motion of the Ether's particles, and therefore it is dependent on the parameter of Space. That is actually Space contains Time, and therefore the Time itself cannot play a role of an axis of a coordinate in principle. It is only value of a distance matter. For a definite size, its own local time will flow. For example, there is no practical reason to measure processes of Galactic motion by scale of life term of Drosophila fly.

The second property of the Ether is a non-uniform distribution of its particles in Space. There are constantly changing sizes of the regions with high and low density of Ether's particles. Irregular distribution of the Ether in Space generates Space anisotropy (Figure 3). The theory of relativity postulating the isotropy of medium (where the speed of light is declared as a constant) has rather weak relations with true reality.

The more particles are placed per unit of volume, the higher is pressure of the Ether (the number of collisions between particles increases), and the higher energy level takes place (the amount of motion also rises). Considering a Black hole from this point

of view, it is such a region in Space, where many motion vectors are spontaneously directed towards a single point. When the maximum concentration of particles is achieved, the Ether's particles under the influence of the predominance of the elastic forces start moving to the regions with a low density of the particles. Ether sparseness occurs in Space, the pressure is reduced.

With the time, some local micro-spaces showing more or less equal distribution of density can spontaneously form rectangular lattices of flashing nodes (the nodes have permanent regular changes in density of the Ether). This type of construction of the crystal lattice is the most natural for the three-dimensional space (significant inequality in Space will lead to other types of crystal lattices reflecting the shape of irregularity). The distance between the nodes of the rectangular lattice will depend on the average density of the Ether in a given area of Space (Figure 4).

The measure of the Ether density is determined by an averaged distance between the particles at a given volume of Space. For the neighborhood of the Earth's surface, where the observation by terrestrial physics is possible, the mean range of the Ether particles before its collision with another particle is within the Planck's wave length, and it is equal to $1,616199(97) \cdot 10^{-35}$ meter.

The ongoing process of formation and decay of Black holes produces between them and the "White" holes laminar flows of the Ether. When two laminar flows are encountered, wide varieties of sizes of Descartes vortices are created. The longest-living type of the Ether vortex has the form of toroid. As an example of the toroid formation is emission of smoke by a smoker (Fig. 5).

Figure 3. Stars sky shows visually the inequality distribution of Energy – Matter in Space

Everything is composed of toroids of different sizes: from elementary particles, electrons, atoms to planets, stars and galactic areas. As they say, all products are cut from the same cloth.

Influence of Ether density irregularities on biochemical reactions

While the concentration of the Ether particle increases in Space, the process of formation of a regular structure starts automatically. Upon reaching high density, the Ether always consists of a crystalline structure (section 3 in Fig. 6) which provides for the maximum accommodation number of the particles at a given volume.

Hypothetically, Space has a certain average density of the Ether particles. This is so-called zero energy level in the Universe. The volume with an excess of the Ethereal particles generates an excess energy potential, which always seeks ways how to neutralize another area with a deficiency of the particles.

If we focus our attention on the level of atoms of chemical elements, we should refer to their base element: a proton. It is suggested the proton is an accelerating vortex of a definite size.

Figure 4. Lattice with nodes of high and low density. In a half of period of density oscillation, large balls are transforming to small ones, but the small ones become large

Due to a centrifugal effect, the acceleration causes a lower inner compression of the Ether, and the vortexes exist as a point with a permanent tendency to absorb the Ether to compensate a deficiency of pressure. There are also vortexes with inhibition of their rotation. In this case, such vortexes are in the process of their decay due to the necessity to emanate the excessive portion of the Ether. It is suggested the decaying vortexes are electrons (possibly it is a decayed vortex of a proton). These above described processes form flows of the Ether from electrons towards protons: the suction force comes into existence. When an electron approaches a proton vortex, the centrifugal forces compensate the force of the suction, and the electron is stabilizing on a definite orbit around the proton (Figure 7).

The suction forces of atoms of chemical elements are determined by the electronegativity factor. This factor indicates how many electrons must be attracted to an atom to reach the neutral condition, when comparing with the Ether's surroundings. A greater imbalance in the Ether density causes a more powerful reactivity of chemical elements and electromagnetic effects.

Figure 5. The toroid formation process

An electrical potential is a difference in the Ether density between two separated volumes in Space. A magnetic flow is an Ether flow seeking for a compensation of the available Ether inhomogeneity or irregularity.

Upon the above detailed considerations, it is quite reasonable to discuss how all above described processes may produce some effects on living organisms.

A deficiency or an excess of electrons in a volume of the body affects parameters of the redox potential and the acid-base balance (the significance of these parameters in metabolism is generally accepted and recognized). In the case of a deficiency of electrons in the given volume, Fluorine, Oxygen or Chlorine are capable to detach them from any substrate in the body. It is dramatically increasing the rate of free radical oxidation to such an intensity that instead of carbohydrates and fats the protein structures will "burn", causing irreversible damage to normal cells. That is why an excess of oxidative processes can be suppressed by the aeration by Chizhevsky's chandelier or by grounding the foot.

If there is an excess of electrons in medium, electronegativity of halogens and oxygen will be compensated, and the body at the expense of previously stored energy will initiate the restoration of cellular structures.

Due to a proper understanding of the crucial role of the electrons in the body,

Figure 6. Compaction of the Ether particles

we can estimate the effect of metabolic changes for different densities of the Ether concentration in Space:

The density of the Ether is increased. Protons receive an additional rotation impetus to accelerate the process of capturing of the Ether to compensate the increased pressure. At the same time, the Ether inflow expels electrons (the electrons themselves emit Ether), the quantitative equilibrium is shifted toward the predominance of protons, and, accordingly, the medium becomes acidified. The activity of the chemical elements - oxidizers (oxygen, fluorine, and chlorine) is sharply enhanced. It means the phase of the Ether excess pressure corresponds to the processes of catabolism, i.e. burning of nutrient substrate to produce energy that is required for the body and partially saved for future needs.

Metabolism is closely associated with some weather condition: when there is a good shiny condition, the Ether pressure is high, and all living organisms feel an excess of vital energy and are engaged in their active life.

The density of the Ether is dropped. At a reduced pressure, the proton vortices begin to slow down and give up electrons easily. The volume freed by the Ether, replaces by unbound electrons. The medium becomes alkaline. The unbound electrons compensate for the action of halogens and oxygen. Reduced rate of oxidative processes activates recovery processes, and the energy saved in the previous catabolic phase is taken to cover recovery needs.

The low density of the Ether accompanies the bad rainy weather: the medium is filled with molecules and electrons (in the atmosphere the water molecules are predominant). All living organisms usually try to conduct their less active lifestyle.

Thus, the regular, periodic change in the density of the Ether in space creates the conditions for the flow of metabolic processes in living organisms in the form of a permanent sequence of anabolic-catabolic phases (Figure 8).

At biophysical level, the Ether's pressure fluctuations are reflected for living organism in the form of changes of geometric dimensions of the structures of the body. Volumes of fluids, blood, cells, compartments and other smaller hierarchical structures up to separate conglomerates of molecules change their sizes cyclically. These changes are accompanied by regular oscillations of medium acidity and redox potential (the absence of pH and redox potential oscillation means death). Due to the fact that 60-80% of the body consists of the water, there are cyclical transient processes of liquids in structures of organism between conditions of gel and sol.

The sol phase corresponds to an alkaline shift of pH of liquid at a high pressure of the Ether against the background of the electrons deficiency, when geometric size of molecules in Space is decreased. Such condition inside cells accompanies active catabolic processes, when the cell preparing to contraction and produce DNA replication.

The gel phase is accompanied by an elevation of acidity in liquids, and

Figure 7. A probable model of Hydrogen. Black lines indicate flows of the Ether, and inside the flow there is an electron

there is a deficiency in the Ether pressure and an excess of electrons; geometric size of molecules is increased. The transition to this phase is determined by an active physical contraction and utilization of substrates stored in the previous Sol phase. During the gel phase, the cell intensively absorbs oxygen and completes its anabolic work.

A living organism differs from a non-living object by existence of free volition. The volition gives an opportunity for living organism to initiate catabolic processes in any period of time independently of the Ether pressure (certainly, catabolic work will be less effective in the anabolic period with low density of the Ether pressure). The free will enables a living organism to move, search for food or to escape from a danger in time, when it is required for vital needs and survival. The accumulation of such energy is provided through the use of microscopic cycles of cellular metabolism, stimulated by the vibrations of the Ether pressure. This process is similar to using an appliance for charging. For example, the efficiency of energy converting of the Ether vibrations in muscle cells of a flea is so high that when the com-

Figure 8. Rotation of metabolic phases is provided synchronically with changes in the Ether's pressure in the environment

pressed protein rezilin is released, the accumulated tension develops a jumping acceleration up to 100G (even astronauts are experiencing acceleration just of 3-4 G).

The life is impossible without vibrations of the Ether pressure. Even minor changes in the spectrum of the vibration during traveling far from the surface of the Earth (on a cosmic orbit or in a mine) may develop serious health problems. It means our genetic vibration profile is adapted to exist exactly on the Earth surface.

A living organism is similar to the Cosmos (Figure 9).

As illustrated in Figure 9, it is evident that the principle established in *Tabula Smaragdina Hermetis*: "Quod est inferius est sicut id quod est superius" has been realized.

Origin of the Primary Elements in Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM). Daily cycle of the Elements sequence

The most important biorhythm, which generates almost all metabolic cycles in every living creature on the Earth, is the circadian (daily) rhythm. This is the natural rhythm of the cosmic process of an interaction between two streams of the Ether in Space, which has spawned the swirling mo-

Figure 9. The similarity of the Space and human structures is amazing: on the left side there is result of Universe modeling made by Max Planck Institute for Astrophysics and on the right side there is a photo of a human bone

tion of the Earth planet with a rotation period of one revolution of 23 hours, 56 minutes and 4 seconds.

Let us investigate the mechanism of the formation of the circadian biorhythms.

Figure 10 below herein shows two essential vectors that form the vortex of the Earth and keep it in a state of equilibrium on the orbit. Points of action of the essential vectors coincide with the Earth's sectors when there is a period of activity of the Fire Minister meridians in TCM. The Fire-Minister Element has its own specific place in the theory of the Five Elements.

There is a stream of the Ether around the Earth in synchronous rotation associated with the physical surface of the planet. This association is of the same type as it is the case with a boundary layer of water moving together with a ship's hull. An interaction between the Ether vector from the Cosmos and the Ether stream associated with the Earth's surface generates areas with different vibrations based on the Doppler Effect. When the two flows encounter (the blue and turquoise areas), they form a higher frequency area as compared with the recession frequency part (the yellow and red areas in Figure 11).

Precisely the same mechanism generates Doppler Ether clouds around the Earth under action of the Ether flow from the Sun (Figure 12).

The combined effect of the two almost opposite flows of the Ether in Space forms the Earth's rotating vortex and the impellent orbital vector which is produced by a geometric sum of two main vectors. Under the influence of the orbital vector of the Ether the summarized Doppler clouds are produced (Figure 13).

In Figure 13 herein we can observe some changes in the wavelength of vibrations from the longest length (Red) to the shortest one (Purple).

Now let's study some designs of traditional Chinese philosophy, namely the one of the main conception: the theory of the Five Elements. In particular, we are interested in the scheme of corresponding of symbols in trigrams with the Primary Elements. Below the diagram of such correspondences is represented (Figure 14).

Where we have the following legend:

- E - Earth,
- Wt - Water,
- Wd - Wood,
- FM - Fire-Minister,
- F - Fire,
- M - Metal.

Further in the text, we'll use the following names and abbreviations for the Primary elements and meridians in a daily circulation:

- Wood Element:
 - Yin Wood - Liver - LR;
 - Yang Wood - Gall Bladder - GB;

Figure 10. Two Ether vectors form rotation of the Earth and produce an impellent orbital vector

Figure 11. Disposition of vibration at the associated stream of the Ether under action of the vector from the Cosmos

Fire Element:

- Yin Fire – Heart – HT;
- Yang Fire – Small intestine – SI;

Earth Element:

- Yin Earth – Spleen – SP;
- Yang Earth – Stomach – ST;

Metal Element:

- Yin Metal – Lungs – LU;
- Yang Metal – Large Intestine – LI;

Water Element:

- Yin Water – Kidneys – KI;
- Yang Waters – Urinary Bladder – BL;

Fire-Minister Element:

- Yin Fire – Minister – Pericardium – PC;
- Yang Fire – Minister – Triple Energizer (Blood) – TE.

Let's return to our trigrams. We suspect (as Leibniz did) that trigrams are simply binary numbers. Then we'll apply to each trigram the number, which is obtained with help of the trigram reading rule in Chinese philosophy from the bottom up. When trigrams are placed in the order of

increasing of numerical values, the traditional sequence of Primary Elements will appear from the right to left by rule of mutual birth: Wood gives rise to Fire, Fire gives rise to the Earth, the Earth gives rise to Metal, Metal gives rise to Water. And probably Fire-Minister is an initiator of the complete cyclicality and can be treated as a connecting link between the end of one cycle and the beginning of the next one. If we make an assumption that a numeric value of trigrams may be associated with a visible color, the following figure may be produced (Figure 15).

The association of the numerical values of trigrams and the Elements with the solar spectrum wavelengths allows us to obtain information about the true color of Chinese Elements and understand this part of information from Chinese philosophy like vibrations with certain frequencies. And certainly we consider these vibrations as the Ether density oscillations. The Ether itself plays a role of pneuma, which generates "ten thousands of entities" in the Chinese philosophical paradigm.

The represented idea is rather fresh in interpretation of the phenomena of Chinese philosophy. Now it is possible to find the information regarding the origin of the colors of the Five Elements. It is suspected, that the widely known correlation is wrong, and it's happened either due to a deliberate distortion, or we are witnessing a degradation of the ancient high-tech expertise.

We assume that the flow of energy transiting via the order of the mutual birth of Elements in the direction from Wood to the Fire Minister Element, i.e. from longer wavelengths to the short ones in the physical world, corresponds to the process of the

Figure 12. Doppler Effect under the Ether vector from the Sun

Figure 13. Summarized Ether aura under action of summarized Ether impellent vector

Ether pressure increasing in our local Space. This position is fully consistent with the physical theories of vortex gravitation, where gravity is a derivative of the Ether drift to the centers of planets and stars. In accordance with this theory, we live in an ever-shrinking world. The results of Space shrinking are the physical effects of the "red shift" and "recession of galaxies" – all

exactly as if we were on the spot of decreasing Alice in Wonderland by Lewis Carroll and observed an increase of all things around from the point of view of geometric sizes.

Further, we made substituting the names of the corresponding Elements by the names of Yin meridians in acupuncture theory of traditional Chinese medicine. The choice of the

E	Wt	Wd	FM	F	M
Gen	Kan	Xun	Zhen	Li	Dui
Shao yang	Tai yin	Shao yang	Shao yin	Tai yang	Shao yang

Figure 14. Scheme of correlation between the Primary Five Elements and trigrams

FM	Wt	M	E	F	Wd
Zhen	Kan	Dui	Gen	Li	Xun
001	010	011	100	101	110
1	2	3	4	5	6

Figure 15. Correspondence of the Five Elements with the solar spectrum

Yin meridians was made for the reason that they are referred to as structural ones because they form the basis of life of the organism (Figure 16).

Knowing that there are two Ether acting vectors available and identifying their activity periods in the daily circulation, taking into account the order of colors for the Doppler's effect of vectors, we have generated the full scheme of meridians and Five Elements circulation (Figure 17).

It was found that the colors of the Five Elements were the result of a superposition of the color components of the acupuncture meridians by the rule of colors synthesis in the visible spectrum (Figure 18).

Green + Red = Yellow

Turquoise + Yellow = Green

Blue + Green = Turquoise

Purple + Turquoise = Blue

Red + Blue = Purple

Yellow + Purple = Red

And here is the color model of daily circulation that represented in the form of wheels (Figure 19).

As you can see, each meridian corresponds to a certain frequency of vibra-

Figure 16. Color of structural (Yin) meridians

Figure 18. The Scheme of the color synthesis

tions and, accordingly, these frequencies are initiated by the process of the daily rotation of the Earth. It is the only reason of the circadian rhythms of metabolic processes in living organisms.

There are colors and meridians associations as indicated below:

- The Red color corresponds to the performance of the Liver (LR) and Urinary Bladder (BL),
- Yellow – Heart (HT) and Large Intestine (LI),
- Green – Pancreas (SP) and Gall Bladder (GB),
- Blue – Lungs (LU) and Small Intestine (SI),
- Blue – Kidney (KI) and Stomach (ST),
- Purple – Pericardium (PC) and Blood (Triple Heater – TE).

In contrast to the conventional scheme of the meridians activity from the traditional Chinese medicine, in our scheme Meridian Yin Fire-Minister (Pericardium) is actually active within the period from 11 a.m. to 01 p.m. due to following reasons:

Firstly, it has its special place between the Elements in Chinese philosophy;

Second, from the physical point of view, the time and place the corre-

Figure 17. The color scheme of daily activity of 12 main acupuncture meridians

Figure 19.

sponding astronomical noon is an application of the force of the Ether flow from the center of the solar system according to the model of the Doppler's effect forming vibration activity acupuncture meridians;

Third, thanks to the hierarchy of the proper meridian frequencies, the wavelength of the Pericardium meridian should be shorter than that of the Heart. This is confirmed by the topology of the location of the meridians on the body – the true pericardium meridian ends at the end of the little finger of the hand, which naturally shorter than the end of the middle finger – the end of the true merid-

ian Heart that says just that messed up only the name of the meridians in the order of the daily circulation, but the true position of the meridians in a daily circulation of activity remained.

All 12 types of vibration are acting simultaneously in the body, but each one prevails within the proper period of the daily circulation. In spite of a living situation of an organism, the circadian rhythm provides for the regular changes via the Ether pressure which creates rhythms of anabolic and catabolic processes for each cell. If the rhythms for some reason are out of synchronization, the energy base of the anabolic-catabolic phases

circulation disappear. Cell falls out of general metabolic stream and dies. Aging is a growing number of dying cells due to a mismatch with rhythms of the Ether medium. Only these rhythms are free and infinite suppliers of energy to create a vibration of vitality.

Association of vibrations of meridians with the energy of 6 Qi

Let's move on to the study of correlation of acupoints to the Primary Elements (in different sources, they are called as transporting (Wu-Shu, Ancient, Barrier) points.

We find that on the Yin meridians Wind Qi points (Wood element) are at the greatest distance from the center of the body (it is suggested as a center of vibrations). Qi points of other Elements are located closer to the center of the vibration in the order of decreasing of their wave length by the order of the mutual birth in the Wu-Xing cycle (Heat, Damp, Wind, Dryness, Cold). Points at Yang meridians are also situated in the order of generation in the direction toward the center of vibration, but they start with the Dryness Qi point (Metal Element), and it indicates the shift between metabolic cycles of the Yin and Yang meridians.

It is clear that the wavelength of points at an equal distance from the center of vibrations cannot differ significantly. Therefore, for further analysis, it is decided to assign to the points of the Yang meridians the similar colors, if they are placed at the similar distance from the center of vibrations (Figure 20).

In the light of the above mentioned suggestions let's try to establish the correlation between 60 Wu-Shu points and the frequencies of the meridians and the Elements (see Fig. 19 herein).

For this purpose, we will use the Wu-Xing law of mutual interrela-

Figure 20. Comparing vibrations between points of Yin and Yang meridians. Please note the points of the Heart and Pericardium meridians are shown here in the traditional order, but in accordance with our conclusions the names of the above mentioned meridians should be changed. The arguments in favor of renaming are presented above in this article

Figure 21. Wu-Xing scheme (Five types of interrelations between vibrations of Elements)

tions between the meridians inside of the Odd or Even system. If we stand on the point of some meridian ("I'm") and activate it, the next me-

ridians will be tonified (Son), the second will be suppressed (Friend), with the third there will be a mutual balance (wife – the acupuncture rule

Meridians, Periods of activity	Points					
	Jing – Well	Ying – Spring	Jing – Well	Yuan	Jing – Well	He – Sea
Gall Bladder GB, 23 – 01	GB-44 BL 7.1 mm	GB-43 HT (t) 5.6 mm	GB-41 GB 4.9 mm	GB-40	GB-38 LU (l) 7.1 mm	GB-34 ST 5.6 mm
Liver LR, 01 – 03	LR-1 LR 7.1 mm	LR-2 LI (l) 5.6 mm	LR-3 SP 4.9 mm		LR-4 KI 5.6 mm	LR-8 TE (t) 4.9 mm
Lungs LU, 03 – 05	LU-11 PC 4.9 mm	LU-10 HT 5.6 mm	LU-9 GB (t) 4.9 mm		LU-8 LU 7.1 mm	LU-5 ST (l) 5.6 mm
Large Intestine LI, 05 – 07	LI-1 LI 5.6 mm	LI-2 SP (l) 4.9 mm	LI-3 SI 7.1 mm	LI-4	LI-5 TE 4.9 mm	LI-11 LR (t) 7.1 mm
Stomach ST, 07 – 09	ST-45 PC (l) 4.9 mm	ST-44 BL 7.1 mm	ST-43 GB 4.9 mm	ST-42	ST-41 LU (t) 7.1 mm	SP-9 KI 5.6 mm
Spleen SP, 09 – 11	SP-1 LR 7.1 mm	SP-2 LI (t) 5.6 mm	SP-3 SP 4.9 mm		SP-5 SI (l) 7.1 mm	SP-9 KI 5.6 mm
Pericardium (It's point of Heart meridian in present interpretation) PC, 11 – 13	HT-9 ST 5.6 mm	HT-8 PC 4.9 mm	HT-7 BL (l) 7.1 mm		HT-4 HT 5.6 mm	HT-3 LU 7.1 mm
Small Intestine SI, 13 – 15	SI-1 TE 4.9 mm	SI-2 LI 5.6 mm	SI-3 SP (t) 4.9 mm	SI-4	SI-5 SI 7.1 mm	SI-8 KI (l) 5.6 mm
Urinary Bladder BL, 15 – 17	BL-67 PC (t) 4.9 mm	BL-66 BL 7.1 mm	BL-65 HT (l) 5.6 mm	BL-64	BL-60 GB 4.9 mm	BL-40 ST 5.6 mm
Kidneys KI, 17 – 19	KI-1 TE (l) 4.9 mm	KI-2 LR 7.1 mm	KI-3 SP 4.9 mm		KI-7 SI (t) 7.1 mm	KI-10 KI 5.6 mm
Heart (It's point of Pericardium in traditional interpretation) HT, 19 – 21	PC-9 BL (t) 7.1 mm	PC-8 HT 5.6 mm	PC-7 GB (l) 4.9 mm		PC-5 LU 7.1 mm	PC-3 PC 4.9 mm
Triple Energizer TE, 21 – 23	TE-1 KI 5.6 mm	TE-2 TE 4.9 mm	TE-3 LR (t) 7.1 mm	TE-4	TE-6 LI 5.6 mm	TE-10 SI (l) 7.1 mm

Figure 22.

“Noon-Midnight”), the fourth meridian will suppress “Ym” (Grandfather, Enemy), and the fifth meridian will activate “Ym” (Mother) (Figure 21).

In Traditional Chinese medicine there is information what Wu-Shu acupuncture points are used to manage each of 12 main acupuncture meridians in accordance with above represented Wu-Xing law. Below in Fig. 22 we have marked each point with the proper color in correlation with

the associated Element and taking into account the Wu-Xing law of Elements interaction. In accordance with Wu-Xing law, tonification point is before the point of the proper meridian (red and yellow arrows up) and sedation point is placed behind the given point (arrows down in Figure 22).

Ether's wave in Space, and on the other hand, a lower Ether pressure makes wavelength longer and decreases the velocity of the wave movement.

Analysis of Qi dynamics

Let's analyze exemplary changes of a wavelength of the Yellow vibration during a day. The length of waves of the Yellow vibrations in periods of activity on the proper meridians will be counted according to the table in Figure 22 herein from the right side to the left one in the increasing order. The right-most cell means volume 1 (One is the shortest wavelength), the left-most cell indicates a volume equal to 5 (Five is the longest wavelength). Volumes for Odd and Even meridians are paired in accordance with dividing the daily cycle into 6 Elements as it is shown in Figure 19 herein.

As you can see in Figure 23, the Even system of meridians (Triple energizer, Liver, Large Intestine, Spleen, Small Intestine, Kidneys) looks like a pulse form in sphygmogram (Figure 24).

The sum of the wavelengths of the Odd and Even systems of meridians (the green line in Figure 23) shows the dynamic character of the wavelengths of the Yellow vibrations during a day. There wavelengths are relatively longer at the time of the Fire and Earth Elements activity (in accordance with the pattern in Figure 19 herein). This period lasts approximately from 23.00 till 07.00 (the red “b” segment in Figure 24), and it is the main daily anabolic phase for the organism when the efficiency of the anabolic process is at the highest level.

The catabolic phase is stipulated by the vibrations of shorter wavelengths (there is a higher pressure of the Ether), and this period takes approximately time from 07.00 till 23.00 (the blue “a” segment in Figure 34 herein).

It is interesting that the ratio between the catabolic and anabolic phases of the daily pulsation is similar to the Golden Ratio.

By the way, the Golden ratio in pulse was discovered by Dr. V. Tsvetkov in 1984 (V.D. Tsvetkov, "Heart, Golden Ratio and Symmetry", published by Department of Scientific and Technical Information of RAS, Pushchino Research Center, 1997).

Where in Figure 25 $t_p(V)/t_s(V)$ and $t_s(V)/t(V)$ are equal to 0.618.

Further evidence of the Doppler principle in the Primary Elements formation.

The fidelity of the Doppler model of the Primary Elements and the meridians can be confirmed further by three physical facts as follows:

The first fact is that the frequency of the first Schumann resonance of the Earth is 7.83 Hertz, which resonates with the frequency of the middle of the visible solar spectrum, with the green area. In our model, the green color is associated with the Yin Earth element (Spleen) and the Yang Wind element (Gall Bladder):

$$7.83 \text{ Hz} = C / (\lambda * 2^{46})$$

Where:

$C = 299\,792\,458 \text{ m/s}$ is the speed of light,

$\lambda = 0,000000544 \text{ m}$ is the wave length of the middle of green color in the visible solar spectrum, and 2^{46} is a factor of octave fractal.

As it is known in traditional Chinese philosophy, the Earth Element plays a special role. Around this Element revolve the remaining four Elements in the Wu-Xing scheme.

The second fact: In the lectures on the physics by famous American scientist Richard Feynman, in Chapter 9, "Electricity in the Atmosphere," paragraph 1 "The electric potential gradient of the atmosphere", there is a daily graph as follows in Figure 26.

Quote of the Feynman lecture:

«The current (in the atmosphere – noted by the Author hereof) varies by

Figure 23.

Figure 24.

about ± 15 percent, and it is largest at 7:00 p.m. in London. The strange part of the thing is that no matter where you measure the current – in the Atlantic Ocean, the Pacific Ocean, or the Arctic Ocean – it is at its peak value when the clocks in London say 7:00 p.m.! All over the world the current is at its maximum at 7:00 p.m. London time and it is at a minimum at 4:00 a.m. London time. In other words, it depends upon the absolute time on the Earth, not upon the local time at the place of observation».

Now we can explain this fact, which seemed surprising to R. Feynman. The Doppler model of Elements has a summarized vector of the Ether flow at 06 p.m. This vector moves the Earth on its orbit. Naturally the maximum of the Ether pressure will be built up at the point of the application of the vector. Increased pressure of the Ether displaces electrons

Figure 25.

from the medium and increases the medium resistance, increases the electrical potential between two vertical points in the atmosphere. A period of the wave of the Ether flow is one day with the wave maximum at 19 Greenwich Mean Time. The shift between 06 p.m. in our model and 07 p.m. in the real physical process indicates the fact that the real meridian of the Ether wave application on the planet is placed towards West from

Figure 26. Daily graph of electric potential in the atmosphere of the Earth at London's time

London. And we have some amazing fact regarding this real zero meridian:

If we study an old map by Mercator prepared in 1595, the zero meridian passes through the western part of Iceland (currently it has a longitude of $17^{\circ} 59' 12''$ W). The one hour of the Earth rotation relatively to the stellar coordinates consists of 15 degrees, which actually corresponds to the arrival of the Ether wave at 18 p.m. of local astronomical time at Iceland and that fits reasonably well our models!

It is worth noting that his maps were designed by Mercator on the basis of some ancient sources, probably inherited from the last civilization catastrophe in the 14th century AD.

It is known that the 14th century by the famous Austrian cultural historian Egon Friedell in his book "Kulturgeschichte der Neuzeit" was given the name "The Last Great Shock", after which the recent history of the survived mankind originates, beginning with the Renaissance. Apparently, Leonardo Da Vinci, the engineering genius of the Renaissance period, based his expertise on a solid foundation of technical knowledge of the former civilization. Even such a minor fact as establishing of the zero meridian demonstrates that previous civilization was more powerful and advanced than ours. Old science was fully aware of the Ether and relied on the natural process, considering it in their cartography, astronomy and obviously medicine (TCM).

Figure 27. Spectrum of Hydrogen atom

Figure 28. Spectrum of Potassium atom

Figure 29. Spectrum of Sodium atom

Figure 30. Spectrum of Magnesium atom

Figure 31. Spectrum of Calcium atom

The third fact: It is in the same quote coming from Feynman lectures: it is said that the lowest electric potential is recorded at 4 a.m. London time. If we change this time to the astronomical time of the correct zero meridian at Iceland, the true time is 5 a.m.. The 5 a.m. in our Doppler model corresponds to the middle of the Earth Element: it is the period when there is the low pressure of the Ether, when the maximum reduction processes in the body (excess of electrons) and the maximum of Yin in Traditional Chinese Medicine is available.

Macroelements by Dr. Samokhotsky

Russian doctor Alexander Samokhotsky (1890-1986), a surgeon, discovered in his long experimental work that almost any disease can be effectively treated by only four macro-

elements: Potassium, Calcium, Magnesium, and Sodium. Regardless of the type of the disease, his mixtures, to be applied on the basis of blood analysis, gave rapid healing effect in most cases.

It was suggested that each of the Primary Elements in Chinese philosophy might be associated with the above macroelements.

The two Primary Elements, namely Fire-Minister and Earth, were excluded from our consideration since in the Doppler model they correspond to the polar level of H^+ and electron concentration (Fire-Minister is an excess of H^+ , but the Earth is an excess of electrons).

To find a correlation of Ca^{++} , Mg^{++} , K^+ and Na^+ with other Primary Elements, we studied spectra of absorption-emission energy in the Ballmer's series of the visible solar spectrum:

As a conclusion we have identified the correlation as follows:

- Fire-Minister – excess of H^+ ;
- Earth – electrons excess (or OH^- radical);
- Wood – Calcium;
- Fire – Potassium;
- Metal – Magnesium;
- Water – Sodium.

Below there is the line of reasoning (Figures 27 – 31):

Hydrogen – Figure 27, Potassium – Figure 28, Sodium – Figure 29, Magnesium – Figure 30, Calcium – Figure 31.

If we submit a smoothed graph of spectral energy power of macroelements, their lines will be represented in Figure 32.

- The Hydrogen graph shows a decline in the power of vibrations in the green area and increases towards the edges, where the purple area is situated (the area of increased acidity). The Hydrogen is associated with the Triple energizer (Blood) and the Pericardium meridians.

- The Potassium graph has the power of the vibrations decreased in the area with the short wavelength, in the field of the blue color. The mid-power spectrum is marked with the yellow color, which was previously identified in correlation with the Fire Element. The minimum of the power of vibrations (the blue color) corresponds to the Element of Water. It is obvious spectral confrontation between the Fire and Water Elements in the daily circulation, and this graph confirms the physical base. Potassium is associated with the Heart and Large Intestine meridians.

- The Sodium graph as opposed to the Potassium graph has the greatest value in the short-wave part of the spectrum, and the average maximum of the power in spectrum is found in the blue color area, but the

Figure 32. Smoothed energy spectra of 4 macroelements

minimum corresponds to the yellow area. Previously, the blue color was determined in correlation with Water Element, and its minimum in the yellow spectrum corresponds to confront with Fire. Sodium is associated with the Kidneys and Stomach meridians.

- The Magnesium graph has a narrow maximal spike in the transition from the green to blue color, while other parts of the spectrum show meager values. In the opinion of the Author hereof, taking into account the established correlation of the four previous macroelements (Hydrogen, Potassium, Sodium and Hydroxyl ion OH^-) with the Primary Elements, the line of Magnesium most likely corresponds to the Metal Element. Magnesium is associated with the Lungs and Small Intestine meridians.

- The Calcium graph demonstrates its smoothed character throughout the spectrum with a moderate level of energy. It produces the only possible correlation with the Wood Element. In favour of this relationship at least two arguments can be presented: a) the Mutual metabolic suppression between Magnesium and Calcium is well known in medicine and on the graphs we can see some kind

of opposition when Magnesium has concentrated energy in the narrow band of spectrum, and Calcium has the scattered energy over the entire spectrum; b) In traditional Chinese medicine the Wood Element (Wind Qi) is responsible for the movement, while Calcium in vivo is directly involved in the contractile processes (Magnesium, on the contrary, promotes relaxation). Calcium is associated with the Liver and Urinary Bladder meridians.

Statement on ethical issues

Research involving people and/or animals is in full compliance with current national and international ethical standards.

Conflict of interest

None declared.

Author contributions

The author read the ICMJE criteria for authorship and approved the final manuscript.

Senior Editorial Manager's Note

To represent Chinese, the author hereof has used one of the original generally accepted Romanization system versions.